

INTERPRETATION OF NOTIONAL RELATIONS INTERWORDS

Matkarimova Shokhista Khabibullaevna

Teacher of the foreign philology department

Urganch state pedagogical institute

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Abstract: Taking into account that words and other linguistic units serve to name and express the subject and event that a person intends to inform others, it is necessary to emphasize that meaning is a phenomenon that reflects the relationship of linguistic units with reality. The article is devoted to the analysis of the interpretation of notional relations interwords.

Keywords: Uzbek, linguistics, vocabulary layer, language, system, lexicology, phases.

It is important to stress that meaning is a phenomena that reflects the interaction of linguistic units with reality since words and other linguistic units help to name and convey the subject and event that a person desires to inform others about. We shouldn't overlook how mystical and significant the word "meaning" is, after all. According to etymological studies, the Uzbek term "ma'no" is closely linked to the words "ma'ni" and "ma'naviy (spiritual)" and has a connotation that is similar to that of intellectual and spiritual richness, substance, and significance.

Linguists have been debating and discussing the idea that the lexical levels of the language have a systematic nature for a very long time. Numerous studies have been conducted in the field of Uzbek linguistics to examine the vocabulary layer of the language as a whole system. Numerous scientific research conducted at various stages in the evolution of the field represent the fundamentals of systematic lexicology. As a result, R. Safarova describes the processes involved in the birth and growth of systematic lexicology in Uzbek linguistics. There are the following phases in their work:

(A) Initial phase. Determine the semantic composition (structure) of some word pairs to see how words differ from lexemes in terms of symbols and methods of breaking them down into constituent parts.

b) the second phase. The study of grouping words into thematic and lexical-semantic categories and dissecting the meaning into its constituent elements is what defines the development stage of systematic lexicology. The foundations of systematic linguistics and systematic lexicology are developed concurrently in the study of grouping words into lexical-semantic units in the lexicology of the Uzbek language. Based on the same basis, the system became a source of research in lexicology as separate lexical-semantic groups, lexical paradigms connected mainly on the basis of synonymous meanings, groups of words with antonymous meaning, various thematic and lexical-semantic lines, lexical paradigms.

By the end of the sixties, along with the lexical-semantic groups known in systematic lexicology in Western European and later Russian linguistics, along with the synonymous and antonymic paradigms, a new type of lexical-semantic relationship between lexical units - hyponymy - is distinguished.

Since the lexical meanings of the language always have a certain relation to each other, according to their meanings, the words are close to each other, negate each other, have opposite meanings, etc. the development of linguistic events can be observed. In the process of researching the theory of some linguists in terms of the meaning they mean from the point

of view of linguistic phenomena, the linguist D.A. Cruz described the research of relations between classes (groups) in his work *Lexical Semantics* as follows:

Under the Congruence category:

1. **identity** (similarity, uniformity):

class A and B have the same members;

A and B class (group) having the same units.

2. **inclusion:**

class B is entirely included in class A;

Class B (group) is fully included in class A (group).

3. **overlap** (to (partially) cover each other, to be partially similar):

class A and class B have members in common but each has members not found in the other;

The phenomenon of having units of class A (group) and class B (group) having common units, as well as having units that are completely different from each other.

4. **disjunction** (not related, different):

class A and class B have no members in common;

Class A (group) and Class B (group) have no common units.

In addition to serving as a model for defining a group of systematic alternatives that apply to practically all other moral connections, the four main relations between the aforementioned classes (groups) serve to create a basic group of moral relations. The fact that basic (root) lexical relations are related to compatibility relations and variations are related to compatibility options serves as a general explanation.

In conclusion, it should be noted that, no matter how much the topics of the field of semantics are discussed, their scope is expanding more and more, and the relationship with other fields of science is becoming stronger, and it is important that it never loses its relevance and relevance, and always invites debate. A.E. As Kibrick said, "the world of languages has no end and is so diverse that no scientific-theoretical fantasy can argue with linguistic reality." Speaking about the issue of the history of semantics, it can be said in the short analysis given above that it did not go through a smooth process like the history of other branches of linguistics. Nevertheless, the fact that not all areas of semantics, which are undergoing "revolutionary" changes in modern linguistics, are not covered on the same scale, is a sign of the need for further deepening and expansion of this research field.

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